

Computational Power and Energy Consumption: The Hidden Challenges of Artificial Intelligence

In our journey to understand the limitations of artificial intelligence, we must first grasp a fundamental truth: AI systems are no different than a car — they need substantial computational resources and energy, just like fuel, to run. The most pressing problem in AI today is this correlation between capabilities and their resource requirements.

Let us consider, for example, a current AI language model working as it processes a simple conversation. Just like our brains need glucose to work, these systems need a lot of electricity to do their work. For context, training a single large language model can generate as much energy as 126 Danish homes do in a whole year (Patterson et al., 2021). This enormous energy need raises serious questions about the sustainability of AI development, both practical and ethical.

Exponentially growing demands from a computational point of view to the complexity of an AI system. Historically, Moore's Law predicted the doubling of computational power every two years, and now we're entering an era that knows the limits to its physicality (Shalf, 2020). Picture yourself trying to fill a glass with water; at some point the glass is unable to hold any more. We are approaching the limits of how many transistors we can put on a silicon chip in the same way.

When we look at the training process of modern AI systems, the challenge is even greater. I compare it to teaching a child – except instead of one teacher engaged with one child, we have millions of virtual teachers operating at the same time, all consuming energy and computational resources. Now, the largest AI models require specialised data centres with thousands of high performance processors working in parallel, consuming enough energy to be equivalent to the energy consumption of small cities (Khalil et al., 2022).

However, critics say the energy consumption used by AI systems is unsustainable and counters international attempts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Importantly, they provide evidence that this carbon footprint of AI training is higher than the carbon emissions of five average American cars over a lifetime (Henderson et al., 2020). But the pro side said that the environmental costs of AI development are short term, while its long-term benefits – optimising energy systems and modelling the climate – would make them sustainable.

AI systems are faced by another crucial challenge of hardware limitations. Traditional computing architectures, based on the von Neumann model, face what we call the "memory wall"—the

growing gap between processor and memory speeds. Now imagine a chef (processor) walking back and forth, back and forth to a refrigerator (memory) in another room all the time. This is an inefficient process that creates bottlenecks that reduce AI system performance and generate unnecessary energy consumption.

Neuromorphic computing emerges as the paradigm change of how we do our AI processing. Traditional computers can only process information sequentially, an example being a single person trying to solve a puzzle by picking apart each piece one by one. On the other hand, neuromorphic computing imitates the capacity of parallel processing of the human brain through billions of neurons acting together. In principle, it could potentially cut energy consumption by several orders of magnitude. For example, IBM's TrueNorth neuromorphic chip ran one million simulated neurons using only 70 milliwatts of power, roughly the power of a hearing aid (Merolla et al., 2014). This foundational work has been extended by more recent developments that take energy efficiency to even higher levels of performance.

Data movement between memory and processing units consumes the bulk of the energy in conventional systems, and neuromorphic systems achieve this efficiency through specially designed hardware that integrates memory and processing into one unit. Picture a classroom where, rather than students constantly walking to a central library (traditional computing), each student has their own set of books right in front of their desk (neuromorphic computing). Still, recent neuromorphic systems still have many ways to go to match the complexity of modern AI tasks. The key issue is to create materials and architectures that will successfully support an accurate analogue state for neural computation while at the same time enduring over time. In Ajayan et al.'s (2022) comprehensive review, note that current neuromorphic devices still face challenges such as device variability, limited endurance, and the requirement for precise control of analogue state, essential for neural computation.

On the other hand, quantum computing proposes an entirely different way to address AI's computational demands. While classical computers process bits in binary states (0 or 1), quantum computers utilize quantum bits, or "qubits," that can exist in multiple states simultaneously through a phenomenon called superposition. Queuing to the combination of quantum entanglement and this property, quantum computers can do some calculations faster exponentially than classical computers. Think of a maze, and a classical computer must try one path after another, while a quantum computer can explore paths simultaneously.

The impact of quantum computing on AI is potentially enormous. If quantum machine learning algorithms could teach complex neural networks in hours instead of weeks and at much less energy, we would be onto something. Gujju et al. (2023) claim that given recent advancements

in quantum hardware (i.e., increased speed, qubit quantity, and quantum volume), quantum machine learning promise has increased significantly. Based upon their comprehensive analysis, they argue that quantum advantage has not yet been proven, but the field has reached promising points in supervised and unsupervised learning techniques, which could potentially unlock quantum mechanics to change how we train machines.

So, current quantum computers face a fundamental challenge of error rates: about one error per hundred operations. To make quantum computers practical, these error rates have to be reduced dramatically: they need to drop from current 10^{-2} to almost the limit of 10^{-12} , one error for one trillion operations. But just bettering physical qubit quality can't deliver the required stability to run the kinds of sophisticated algorithms that require millions or billions of operations.

A solution to this problem exists in quantum error correction (QEC): information is encoded across multiple physical qubits, resulting in more reliable logical qubits. The practical QEC threshold requires physical two-qubit gate fidelity of 99.9% (error rate of 10^{-3}), known as "the three nines." It is also incredible that different qubit technologies have made great progress towards that goal—ion traps and superconducting qubits have already crossed the QEC threshold, while neutral atoms and silicon qubits are on their way.

Having crossed the threshold is not enough. The high fidelity must be both consistent across all qubits and stable over time, alongside measurements and reset operations that are themselves reliable, and the QEC overhead — the ratio of physical to logical qubits — must be manageable. To achieve these requirements, companies will have to work on reducing costs per qubit and improving power efficiency, and classical QEC technologies will have to be implemented to get there rather than seeking to improve fidelity further. (Riverlane, 2024).

With that said, the challenges above are no stopping ground for neuromorphic and quantum computing. Researchers are trying to find the perfect hybrid approach, which takes the best from each computing paradigm alternative. For example, some suggest using quantum processors for one type of training task and neuromorphic systems for inference and real time processing. It is much like how we would use a supercomputer to model complex weather, but we rely on local sensors to read the daily temperature.

Conclusion

There are a plethora of technological limitations, environmental concerns, and practical constraints to overcome in achieving power and energy consumption capabilities critical to AI

development. While we expand the envelope of what can be accomplished with AI, we must also seek to create smarter, more energy-efficient computing architectures and more efficient energy solutions. Not only is this the future of AI, but our ability to do so with the power to be sustainable and responsible is critical to its future.

References

- [1] Ajayan, J., Nirmal, D., Jebalin, B. K., IV, & Sreejith, S. (2022). Advances in neuromorphic devices for the hardware implementation of neuromorphic computing systems for future artificial intelligence applications: A critical review. *Microelectronics Journal*, *130*, 105634. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mejo.2022.105634>
- [2] Gujju, Y., Matsuo, A., & Raymond, R. (2023). Quantum Machine Learning on Near-Term Quantum Devices: Current state of supervised and Unsupervised techniques for Real-World Applications. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2307.00908>
- [3] Henderson, P., Hu, J., Romoff, J., Brunskill, E., Jurafsky, D., & Pineau, J. (2020). Towards the systematic reporting of the energy and carbon footprints of machine learning. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2002.05651>
- [4] Khalil, M., McGough, A. S., Pourmirza, Z., Pazhoohesh, M., & Walker, S. (2022). Machine Learning, Deep Learning and Statistical Analysis for forecasting building energy consumption — A systematic review. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, *115*, 105287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.105287>
- [5] Merolla, P. A., Arthur, J. V., Alvarez-Icaza, R., Cassidy, A. S., Sawada, J., Akopyan, F., Jackson, B. L., Imam, N., Guo, C., Nakamura, Y., Brezzo, B., Vo, I., Esser, S. K., Appuswamy, R., Taba, B., Amir, A., Flickner, M. D., Risk, W. P., Manohar, R., & Modha, D. S. (2014). A million spiking-neuron integrated circuit with a scalable communication network and interface. *Science*, *345*(6197), 668–673. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1254642>
- [6] Patterson, D., Gonzalez, J., Le, Q., Liang, C., Munguia, L., Rothchild, D., So, D., Texier, M., & Dean, J. (2021). Carbon emissions and large neural network training. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2104.10350>
- [7] Riverlane. (n.d.). *Quantum error correction Report 2024 - Riverlane*. Riverlane. <https://www.riverlane.com/quantum-error-correction-report-2024>
- [8] Shalf, J. (2020). The future of computing beyond Moore's Law. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society a Mathematical Physical and Engineering Sciences*, *378*(2166), 20190061. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2019.0061>